

We are glad to welcome you to HYBRIS' first newsletter!

Funded by the European Union, HYBRIS is a Horizon 2020 project involving 15 partners spread across 6 countries for a 3 year long series of developments to achieve a new generation of battery-based hybrid storage solutions for smarter, sustainable and more energy efficient grids and behind-the-meter systems.

At HYBRIS, we know that high-quality and technologically innovative batteries are key to reach the goals of the European Green Deal and contribute to the zero-pollution ambition set in it.

HYBRIS – YEAR 1!

The first year of the project has been oriented by the need to define the requirements of the new hybrid storage system and its application contexts, together with the first developments and characterization of the enhanced battery components.

NEWS

TOSHIBA BATTERIES MAIN FEATURES AND OPTIMIZATION (PART III/III)

The last article on Toshiba batteries provides information regarding their electrical safety and thermal stability, and the probability of lithium metal deposition. Toshiba also explains where they are manufactured and the production process.

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TOSHIBA BATTERIES MAIN FEATURES AND OPTIMIZATION (PART II/III)

In this second part of Toshiba article, you get to know some more characteristics of its battery, including lifetime, its chemical composition, temperature dependencies and charge characteristics. It includes a comparison with other battery chemistries.

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TOSHIBA BATTERIES MAIN FEATURES AND OPTIMIZATION (PART I/III)

Toshiba, as one of the two battery manufacturers of the project, shows its SCiB™ battery and main features, and also its battery management system for health and safety of modules.

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HYBRIS: A PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF ITS ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS

Our partner Lomartov, with the main support of the battery manufacturers of the project Toshiba and Kemiwatt, introduces the report on the Levelized Cost of Storage analysis of the Hybrid Energy Storage System, preliminarily providing its economic competitiveness.

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CLUSTERING EVENT FOR H2020 BATTERIES PROJECTS

HYBRIS participated on the virtual Clustering Event for H2020 Batteries Projects on November 17th-18th, 2021. Organized by the EC, the event aimed at bringing together 35 projects developing batteries and battery systems, both in the energy and in the transport sector.

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HYBRIS PROJECT IS PART OF FLORES!

Since September 2021, HYBRIS is part of FLORES, the Network of Flow Battery Research Initiatives made up of 14 EU-funded projects. FLORES has been created under the Horizon Results Booster and has been set up by the project FlowCamp. The projects share their ideas and results in order to create next generation energy storage systems for more stable, effective and affordable energy sources.

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HYBRIS FIRST GENERAL ASSEMBLY

On 1&2 July 2021, the HYBRIS consortium got together for the first time after the kick-off meeting in January 2021. The goal of this first meeting was to discuss the progress made in the first six months and coordinate the future work. The consortium also discussed the importance of defining the working conditions in each use case, as they will have a strong impact on the state of the batteries to be implemented.

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PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

Main Outcomes of WPI: Materials Assessment and Simplified LCA

The main milestone achieved at this stage is the completion of the materials assessment and a first simplified Life Cycle Assessment. It covers a preliminary assessment of the sustainability performance of lithium and flow batteries used in the hybridised scheme, safety of the employed materials, a study on current recycling routes for both batteries' chemistries and relevant eco-design recommendations.

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